

The MEANS Procedure

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Analysis Variable : Swing

limb	N	Obs	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.0741628	0.0730000	0.0079479	0.0510000	0.0970000
1	129	129	0.0745581	0.0740000	0.0087669	0.0540000	0.1050000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.07416	0.001052
2	limb	1	0.07455	0.001052

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.00040	0.000733	-0.54	0.5902		swing

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Analysis Variable : PSwingStride

limb	N	Obs	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	37.2767442	37.2000000	2.0479987	31.5000000	44.7000000
1	129	129	37.3697674	37.3000000	2.7608198	24.4000000	44.7000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	37.2752	0.2791
2	limb	1	37.3682	0.2791

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.09302	0.2454	-0.38	0.7050		PSwingStride

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Analysis Variable : Brake

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.0241163	0.0230000	0.0064282	0.0090000	0.0520000
1	129	129	0.0268605	0.0250000	0.0069785	0.0130000	0.0510000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.02411	0.000584
2	limb	1	0.02685	0.000584

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.00274	0.000849	-3.23	0.0014	***	Brake

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Analysis Variable : PBrakeStride

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	12.1813953	11.8000000	3.4015798	4.7000000	27.8000000
1	129	129	13.5565891	12.9000000	3.7620399	7.7000000	25.8000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	12.1787	0.3342
2	limb	1	13.5539	0.3342

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-1.3752	0.4382	-3.14	0.0019	***	PBrakeStride

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Analysis Variable : Propel

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.1004186	0.1010000	0.0109199	0.0640000	0.1290000
1	129	129	0.0978915	0.0980000	0.0122297	0.0700000	0.1450000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.1004	0.001410
2	limb	1	0.09790	0.001410

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.002527	0.001076	2.35	0.0198	***	Propel

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Analysis Variable : PPropelStride

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	50.5410853	51.0000000	3.6474651	33.9000000	57.8000000
1	129	129	49.0666667	49.1000000	4.1812516	39.3000000	65.3000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	50.5453	0.3920
2	limb	1	49.0709	0.3920

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	1.4744	0.4583	3.22	0.0015	***	PPropelStride

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Analysis Variable : Stance

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.1245194	0.1240000	0.0092408	0.0840000	0.1460000
1	129	129	0.1247442	0.1240000	0.0105195	0.0990000	0.1680000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.1245	0.001289
2	limb	1	0.1247	0.001289

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.00022	0.000776	-0.29	0.7723		Stance

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Analysis Variable : PStanceStride

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	62.7232558	62.8000000	2.0479987	55.3000000	68.5000000
1	129	129	62.6302326	62.7000000	2.7608198	55.3000000	75.6000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	62.7248	0.2791
2	limb	1	62.6318	0.2791

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.09302	0.2454	0.38	0.7050		PStanceStride

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Analysis Variable : Stride

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.1986589	0.1970000	0.0152625	0.1350000	0.2400000
1	129	129	0.1992713	0.1980000	0.0156274	0.1640000	0.2390000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.1987	0.002067
2	limb	1	0.1993	0.002067

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.00061	0.001132	-0.54	0.5891		Stride

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Analysis Variable : PBrakeStance

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	19.4046512	18.6000000	5.3348334	7.5000000	45.1000000
1	129	129	21.6310078	20.7000000	5.8103598	12.7000000	39.3000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	19.4000	0.5194
2	limb	1	21.6263	0.5194

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-2.2264	0.6825	-3.26	0.0013	***	PBrakeStance

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Analysis Variable : PPropelStance

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	80.5953488	81.4000000	5.3348334	54.9000000	92.5000000
1	129	129	78.3689922	79.3000000	5.8103598	60.7000000	87.3000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	80.6000	0.5194
2	limb	1	78.3737	0.5194

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	2.2264	0.6825	3.26	0.0013	***	PPropelStance

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Analysis Variable : StanceoverSwing

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	1.6914729	1.7000000	0.1468582	1.2000000	2.2000000
1	129	129	1.6945736	1.7000000	0.2240641	1.2000000	3.1000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	1.6916	0.02105
2	limb	1	1.6947	0.02105

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.00310	0.01996	-0.16	0.8767		StanceoverSwing

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Analysis Variable : StrideLength

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	5.5674419	5.5000000	0.4283257	3.8000000	6.7000000
1	129	129	5.5852713	5.6000000	0.4360871	4.6000000	6.7000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	5.5672	0.05787
2	limb	1	5.5851	0.05787

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.01783	0.03166	-0.56	0.5739		StrideLength

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Analysis Variable : StrideFreq

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	5.1627907	5.1000000	0.4330253	4.2000000	7.6000000
1	129	129	5.1527132	5.2000000	0.4073691	4.2000000	6.3000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	5.1628	0.05436
2	limb	1	5.1528	0.05436

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.01008	0.03378	0.30	0.7657		StrideFreq

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Analysis Variable : PawAngle

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	-15.3209302	-15.8000000	4.0124547	-26.2000000	-5.2000000
1	129	129	14.9844961	14.4000000	3.5609964	5.9000000	25.8000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	-15.3237	0.3647
2	limb	1	14.9817	0.3647

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-30.3054	0.4559	-66.48	<.0001	***	PawAngle

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Analysis Variable : AbsolutePawAngle

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	15.3209302	15.8000000	4.0124547	5.2000000	26.2000000
1	129	129	14.9844961	14.4000000	3.5609964	5.9000000	25.8000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	15.3257	0.4187
2	limb	1	14.9893	0.4187

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.3364	0.3976	0.85	0.3984		AbsolutePawAngle

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Analysis Variable : PawAngleVar

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	3.7224806	3.3000000	1.7463462	1.3000000	8.9000000
1	129	129	3.6550388	3.3000000	1.7217797	1.1000000	10.7000000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	3.7214	0.1828
2	limb	1	3.6539	0.1828

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.06744	0.1870	0.36	0.7187		PawAngleVar

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Analysis Variable : SLVar

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.7374419	0.7000000	0.2684017	0.2900000	1.9700000
1	129	129	0.7734884	0.7500000	0.2562184	0.2700000	2.2600000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.7364	0.02777
2	limb	1	0.7725	0.02777

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.03605	0.02817	-1.28	0.2021		SLVar

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Analysis Variable : NumSteps

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	16.0348837	16.0000000	4.1350191	8.0000000	26.0000000
1	129	129	16.1976744	16.5000000	4.1497452	8.0000000	26.0000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	16.0445	0.4713
2	limb	1	16.2073	0.4713

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.1628	0.4170	-0.39	0.6967		NumSteps

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Analysis Variable : StrideLengthCV

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	13.4646512	12.2400000	5.8007790	5.2100000	52.0000000
1	129	129	14.0566667	13.1700000	5.5129989	5.4200000	49.0600000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	13.4446	0.6073
2	limb	1	14.0366	0.6073

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.5920	0.5961	-0.99	0.3218		StrideLengthCV

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Analysis Variable : SwingDurationCV

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	16.2397674	14.6200000	6.5740770	7.5800000	65.9500000
1	129	129	16.8773643	15.7300000	6.3012740	8.0500000	46.4400000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	16.2217	0.6731
2	limb	1	16.8592	0.6731

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.6376	0.7151	-0.89	0.3736		SwingDurationCV

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Analysis Variable : PawAreaPeak

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.6493023	0.6500000	0.1042322	0.2300000	0.9700000
1	129	129	0.6034884	0.6100000	0.1052055	0.1700000	0.9100000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.6493	0.01244
2	limb	1	0.6035	0.01244

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.04581	0.009808	4.67	<.0001	***	PawAreaPeak

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Analysis Variable : PawAreaVarPeak

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.0396899	0.0300000	0.0282273	0.0100000	0.1600000
1	129	129	0.0383721	0.0300000	0.0227002	0.0100000	0.1400000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.03965	0.002440
2	limb	1	0.03833	0.002440

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.001318	0.002912	0.45	0.6513		PawAreaVarPeak

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Analysis Variable : pSharedStance

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	41.9860465	40.2000000	9.1760196	25.6000000	80.1000000
1	129	129	41.8511628	40.6000000	8.7933846	26.0000000	82.0000000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	41.9708	0.9955
2	limb	1	41.8359	0.9955

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.1349	0.9466	0.14	0.8868		pSharedStance

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Analysis Variable : GaitSymmetry

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	1.0086047	1.0100000	0.0416035	0.8600000	1.3800000
1	129	129	1.0086047	1.0100000	0.0416035	0.8600000	1.3800000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	1.0087	0.004387
2	limb	1	1.0087	0.004387

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-918E-22	0.004514	-0.00	1.0000		GaitSymmetry

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Analysis Variable : MAXdAdT

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	68.5874419	68.7400000	11.9059608	20.3000000	103.5500000
1	129	129	62.8423256	63.4900000	11.8504913	15.6000000	98.1600000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	68.5984	1.4309
2	limb	1	62.8533	1.4309

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	5.7451	1.1044	5.20	<.0001	***	MAXdAdT

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The MEANS Procedure

Analysis Variable : MINdAdT

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	-10.1858915	-9.8900000	1.8144010	-17.2000000	-6.8800000
1	129	129	-10.1605426	-10.1100000	1.6818996	-17.8500000	-6.1500000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	-10.1821	0.1680
2	limb	1	-10.1568	0.1680

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.02535	0.1982	-0.13	0.8984		MINdAdT

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Analysis Variable : TauPropulsion

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.1414512	0.1220000	0.0997871	-0.3114000	0.5707000
1	129	129	0.0718426	0.1011000	0.3706533	-3.0238000	0.3718000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.1414	0.02406
2	limb	1	0.07182	0.02406

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	0.06961	0.03377	2.06	0.0405	***	TauPropulsion

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Analysis Variable : OverlapDistance

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.4855039	0.8500000	1.2965555	-7.2400000	2.3000000
1	129	129	0.5345736	0.7400000	0.9016989	-5.7200000	1.7400000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.4870	0.1022
2	limb	1	0.5361	0.1022

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.04907	0.1354	-0.36	0.7175		OverlapDistance

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Analysis Variable : PawPlacementPositioning

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.3498450	0.3600000	0.2304106	-0.3100000	1.1300000
1	129	129	0.3728682	0.4000000	0.2470109	-0.3200000	1.0200000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.3495	0.02090
2	limb	1	0.3725	0.02090

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.02302	0.03007	-0.77	0.4448		PawPlacementPositioning

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Analysis Variable : AtaxiaCoefficient

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	0.4934109	0.4500000	0.2042000	0.1800000	1.6000000
1	129	129	0.5187597	0.4700000	0.2163187	0.2400000	1.8400000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	0.4930	0.02206
2	limb	1	0.5183	0.02206

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Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.02535	0.02320	-1.09	0.2759		AtaxiaCoefficient

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Analysis Variable : MidlineDistance

limb	N Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	1.1286822	1.1600000	0.4483692	-0.3700000	2.8500000
1	129	129	1.2793798	1.2900000	0.4396567	-0.8500000	2.9100000

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Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	1.1289	0.04662
2	limb	1	1.2796	0.04662

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.1507	0.04783	-3.15	0.0019	***	MidlineDistance

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Analysis Variable : AxisDistance

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	-1.0681395	-1.0800000	0.1234135	-1.4200000	-0.7300000
1	129	129	1.1039535	1.0900000	0.1211947	0.8300000	1.5900000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	-1.0682	0.009656
2	limb	1	1.1039	0.009656

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-2.1721	0.01613	-134.70	<.0001	***	AxisDistance

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Analysis Variable : PawDrag

limb	Obs	N	Mean	Median	Std Dev	Minimum	Maximum
0	129	129	-6.1879922	-6.4070000	1.7570369	-11.8760000	-2.0720000
1	129	129	-5.5825736	-5.6140000	1.8144040	-10.3710000	-1.4320000

Obs	Effect	limb	Estimate	StdErr
1	limb	0	-6.1907	0.1912
2	limb	1	-5.5853	0.1912

Obs	Effect	Estimate	StdErr	tValue	Probt	sig	variable
1	limb	-0.6054	0.1931	-3.14	0.0020	***	PawDrag